

Metadata template¹ for datasets of *L&O-Letters* articles

Table 1. Satellite-derived chlorophyll *a*.

Satellite-derived chlorophyll concentrations (Chl_{sat})	<i>Chl_{sat} data (1998-2018) derived from the regional algorithm of the Marine Hydrophysical Institute in Sevastopol (MHI-product).</i>
URL of dataset	<i>This is forthcoming upon decision at the first review stage.</i>
Abstract	<i>We have analysed the seasonal variation in phytoplankton carbon biomass and occurrences of blooms in the open Black Sea by combining in situ carbon-to chlorophyll <i>a</i> ratios from the open Black Sea covering the entire seasonal cycle with satellite chlorophyll <i>a</i> data (1998-2018) to obtain a comprehensive proxy data set for phytoplankton carbon biomass in the surface layer. Data from three satellite instruments (SeaWiFS, 1997–2010; MODIS (Aqua), 2002–2018; and MODIS (Terra), 2000–2018) have been used to produce five-day composite Chl_{sat} for rectangular areas of 0.3° longitude and latitude, which were grouped into six larger regions associated with different types of water circulation in the open Black Sea. The average Chl_{sat} for each region was calculated and is presented in dataset.</i>
Keywords	<i>Chlorophyll <i>a</i>, carbon phytoplankton biomass, remote sensing</i>
Lead author for the dataset	<i>Vyacheslav V. Suslin</i>
Title and position of lead author	<i>Principle investigator</i>
Organization and address of lead author	<i>Marine Hydrophysical Institute RAS, Kapitanskaya str., 2, Sevastopol 299011, Russia.</i>
Email address of lead author	<i>Slava.suslin@mhi-ras.ru</i>
Additional authors or contributors to the dataset	
Organization associated with the data	
Funding	<i>Vyacheslav V. Suslin research was supported by international projects DEVOTES and PERSEUS of the 7th framework programme of the European Community.</i>
License	CCO
Geographic location – verbal description	<i>The open Black Sea</i>
Geographic coverage bounding coordinates	<i>Long, E = 28⁰ – 42⁰; Lat, N = 41⁰ - 47⁰</i>
Time frame - Begin date	<i>July 1998</i>
Time frame - End date	<i>June 2018</i>
General study design	<i>In this research, Level 2 data (products of standard atmosphere correction at three bands filtered by masks/flags) of SeaWiFS, MODIS (on Terra and Aqua satellites), and MERIS scanners were retrieved for their mission lifetime.</i>
Methods description	<i>The main concept of MHI-product is to isolate, from the total light absorption, two, generally, independently variable components associated with the absorption of light by nonliving (dissolved organic matter + detrite)</i>

¹ This document liberally borrows from a similar document provided by the Environmental Data Initiative
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	<i>and living (phytoplankton) organic matter (Suslin et al., 2008, Suslin and Churilova, 2016). To implement this algorithm, satellite data of the second level (Level 2) of 1×1 km spatial resolution were used. These data were the result of atmospheric correction of three satellite instruments (SeaWiFS, 1997 - 2011 and MODIS from Aqua, 2000 - 2018 and Terra, 2002 - 2018) after elimination of the situations that could distort the values of the sea brightness coefficient and eventually lead to gross errors in the calculation of Chl a concentration. For this purpose, the quality criteria of the satellite product (masks and flags) from the standard set contained in the product Level 2 were used (Suslin and Churilova, 2016).</i>
Laboratory, field, or other analytical methods	<i>Not applicable.</i>
Taxonomic species or groups	<i>Not applicable.</i>
Quality control	<i>The use of this regional algorithm (MHI-product) was determined to its significantly lower relative error of Chl_{sat} recovery (30-50%) compared to the error of Chl_{sat} recovery in the Black Sea according to the standard NASA algorithm (200-400%) (Suslin et al. 2018).</i>
Additional information	<i>Suslin, V.V., Churilova, T.J., Sosik, H.M., 2008. The SeaWiFS algorithm of chlorophyll a in the Black Sea. Marine Ecological Journal VII (2), 24 – 42 (in Russian, doi: 10.21072/mbj.2019.04.4.05) Suslin, V.V., Churilova, T.J., 2016. A regional algorithm for separating light absorption by chlorophyll-a and coloured detrital matter in the Black Sea, using 480–560 nm bands from ocean colour scanners. International Journal of Remote Sensing, 37:18, 4380–4400. doi:10.1080/01431161.2016.1211350 Suslin, V.V., Churilova, T.J., Li, M., Moncheva, S., Finenko, Z.Z., 2018. Comparison of the Black Sea chlorophyll-a algorithms for SeaWiFS and MODIS instruments. Fundamental and Applied Hydrophysics 11 (3), 64–72 (in Russian) doi:10.1080/22797254.2018.1533389.</i>

Table 2. Data dictionary: description of the variables (i.e., columns) in satellite-derived chlorophyll *a* dataset.

Column name	Description	Units	Code explanation	Data format	Missing data code
<i>M/D/Y</i>	<i>Month/Day/Year</i>				
<i>Chl_R1</i>	<i>It is a five-day composite and average for Region 1 Chl_{sat} concentrations, having the normal distribution</i>	<i>mg m⁻³</i>	<i>Chl = Chl_{sat}; R1 = Region 1 (Fig. 1).</i>		
<i>Out_R1</i>	<i>It is five-day composite and average for</i>	<i>mg m⁻³</i>	<i>Out = outliers; R1 = Region 1(Fig. 1).</i>		

	<i>Region 1 Chl_{sat} concentrations, exceeding the 99th percentile of the normal distribution</i>				
<p>The remaining columns show the corresponding Chl_{sat} and <i>Out</i> for Regions 2-6.</p> <p>Regional coordinates: R1 (29.6° E, 43.05° N – 32.4° E, 43.9° N); R2 (30.6° E, 42.5° N – 32.5° E, 43.05° N); R3 (29.9° E, 41.7° N – 33.2° E, 42.4° N); R4 (35.1° E, 44.1° N – 38.9° E, 43.4° N); R5 (35.9° E, 43.4° N – 37.8° E, 43.0° N); R6 (35.2° E, 42.7° N – 38.3° E, 41.8° N).</p>					

Table 3. Phytoplankton Carbon biomass.

Phytoplankton carbon biomass (C_{sat})	<i>C_{sat} data (1998-2018) were converted from Chl_{sat} using the monthly mean carbon-to-Chl a ratio.</i>
URL of dataset	<i>This is forthcoming upon decision at the first review stage.</i>
Abstract	<i>We have analysed the seasonal variation in phytoplankton carbon biomass and occurrences of blooms in the open Black Sea by combining in situ carbon-to chlorophyll a ratios from the open Black Sea covering the entire seasonal cycle with satellite chlorophyll a data (1998-2018) to obtain a comprehensive proxy data set for phytoplankton carbon biomass in the surface layer. Computed monthly means of C:Chla were used for converting Chl_{sat} to carbon biomass (C_{sat}). Time series of the average 5-day composite Chl_{sat} and C_{sat} for each of the six regions were separated into a base seasonal pattern and outliers. In the case of C_{sat}, outliers were defined as phytoplankton blooms.</i>
Keywords	<i>Chlorophyll a, phytoplankton carbon biomass, seasonality, phytoplankton blooms</i>
Lead author for the dataset	<i>Oleg A. Yunev</i>
Title and position of lead author	<i>Principle investigator</i>
Organization and address of lead author	<i>Moscow representative office A.O. Kovalevsky Institute of Biology of the Southern Seas of RAS, Leninski prosp., 38, build. 3, Moscow 119991, Russia</i>
Email address of lead author	<i>o.yunev@ibss-ras.ru</i>
Additional authors or contributors to the dataset	
Organization associated with the data	
Funding	<i>Oleg A. Yunev research was supported by Russian Foundation for Basic Research “Functional, metabolic and toxicological aspects of the existence of aquatic organisms and their populations in habitats with different physical and chemical regime” (theme No. AAAA-A18-118021490093-4)</i>
License	CCO
Geographic location – verbal description	<i>The open Black Sea</i>
Geographic coverage	<i>Long, E = 28° – 42°; Lat, N = 41° - 47°</i>

bounding coordinates	
Time frame - Begin date	<i>July 1998</i>
Time frame - End date	<i>June 2018</i>
General study design	<i>Our study is the first to assemble C:Chl a from the open Black Sea covering the entire seasonal cycle, and combine it with satellite imagery to obtain a comprehensive proxy data set for phytoplankton carbon biomass in the surface layer.</i>
Methods description	<i>C_{sat} data (1998-2018) were converted from Chl_{sat} by multiplying satellite data by the average monthly carbon-to-Chl a ratio.</i>
Laboratory, field, or other analytical methods	<i>Not applicable.</i>
Taxonomic species or groups	<i>Not applicable.</i>

Table 4. Data dictionary: description of the variables (i.e., columns) in C_{sat} dataset.

Column name	Description	Units	Code explanation	Data format	Missing data code
<i>M/D/Y</i>	<i>Month/Day/Year</i>				
<i>C_R1</i>	<i>It is a five-day composite and average for Region 1 C_{sat} concentrations, having the normal distribution</i>	<i>mg C m⁻³</i>	<i>C = C_{sat}; R1 = Region 1 (Fig. 1).</i>		
<i>Bloo_R1</i>	<i>It is five-day composite and average for Region 1 C_{sat} concentrations, exceeding the 99th percentile of the normal distribution and defined as phytoplankton blooms</i>	<i>mg C m⁻³</i>	<i>Bloo = outliers, defined as phytoplankton blooms; R1 = Region 1(Fig. 1).</i>		
<p>The remaining columns show the corresponding C_{sat} and Bloo for Regions 2-6.</p> <p>Regional coordinates: R1 (29.6° E, 43.05° N – 32.4° E, 43.9° N); R2 (30.6° E, 42.5° N – 32.5° E, 43.05° N); R3 (29.9° E, 41.7° N – 33.2° E, 42.4° N); R4 (35.1° E, 44.1° N – 38.9° E, 43.4° N); R5 (35.9° E, 43.4° N – 37.8° E, 43.0° N); R6 (35.2° E, 42.7° N – 38.3° E, 41.8° N).</p>					

Table 5. Carbon-to-Chl a ratio

Carbon-to-Chl a ratio (C:Chl a)	<i>C:Chl a ratio derived from simultaneous in situ measurements of carbon phytoplankton biomass and chlorophyll a concentration</i>
URL of dataset	<i>This is forthcoming upon decision at the first review stage.</i>
Abstract	<i>We have analysed the seasonal variation in phytoplankton carbon biomass and occurrences of blooms in the open Black Sea. In situ C:Chl a ratio, from R/V cruises during 1988-2013 in the open Black Sea, were assembled from various sources. For calculating carbon biomass, algae cells with linear</i>

	<i>dimensions of more than 2 μm (algae related to nano- and microphytoplankton) were counted using an inverted microscopy and converted to cell volume using measured dimensions and species-specific geometric formulas.</i>
Keywords	<i>Carbon phytoplankton biomass, chlorophyll a, microscopy</i>
Lead author for the dataset	<i>Ludmila V. Stelmakh</i>
Title and position of lead author	<i>Principle investigator</i>
Organization and address of lead author	<i>Moscow representative office A.O. Kovalevsky Institute of Biology of the Southern Seas of RAS, Leninski prosp., 38, build. 3, Moscow 119991, Russia</i>
Email address of lead author	<i>l.stelmakh@ibss-ras.ru</i>
Additional authors or contributors to the dataset	
Organization associated with the data	
Funding	<i>The work is conducted with partial support of RFFR project "Alternative approach to phytoplankton biomass and growth rate in the Black Sea evaluation by satellite data" (№ 16-05-00076) and in the framework of the state assignment on topic "Functional, metabolic and toxicological aspects of aquatic organisms existence and their populations in habitats with different physical and chemical regime" (theme No.16-05-00268).</i>
License	CCO
Geographic location – verbal description	<i>The open Black Sea</i>
Geographic coverage bounding coordinates	<i>Long, E = 28⁰ – 42⁰; Lat, N = 41⁰ - 47⁰</i>
Time frame - Begin date	<i>March 1988</i>
Time frame - End date	<i>May 2013</i>
General study design	
Methods description	<i>The determination of Chl a concentration was carried out using standard methods (spectrophotometric and fluorimetric), the comparison of which showed close results (Yunev et al., 2002). The abundance and linear dimensions of algae cells were determined in a 0.1 ml drop with three – five replications under light microscope ZEISS Primo Star, which makes it possible to clearly distinguish between algae cells with linear dimensions of more than 2 μm (algae related to nano- and microphytoplankton). Linear measurements were converted to cell volume using various geometric formulas. Average cell volume of phytoplankton was determined as a ratio of total volume for all cells to their abundance. Phytoplankton organic carbon concentration was calculated from average cell volume for each species of diatoms and dinoflagellates using the equations presented in the work (Menden-Deuer & Lessard 2000), for coccolithophorid <i>Emiliania huxley</i> – using the equation (Montagnes et al. 1994), for other algae – using the equation (Strathmann 1967). Phytoplankton species identification was carried out using the manual (Tomas 1997).</i>
Laboratory, field, or other analytical methods	<i>Simultaneous measurements were made in seawater samples from the same bathometer in R/V cruises of 1988-1996 (Black Sea Data Base, 2003) and in the same concentrated samples of phytoplankton in R/V cruises of</i>

	2005 – 2013 (Stelmakh, 2018).
Taxonomic species or groups	
Quality control	
Additional information	Yunev, O.A., et al., 2002. Long-term variations of surface chlorophyll a and primary production in the open Black Sea. <i>Mar. Ecol. Prog. Ser.</i> 230, 11–28. doi:10.3354/meps230011; Menden-Deuer, S., Lessard, E.J., 2000. Carbon to volume relationships for dinoflagellates, diatoms and other protist plankton. <i>Limnol. Oceanogr.</i> 45, 569–579. doi:10.4319/lo.2000.45.3.0569; Montagnes, D.J., et al., 1994. Estimating carbon, nitrogen, protein and chlorophyll a from volume in marine phytoplankton. <i>Limnol. Oceanogr.</i> 39, 1044–1060. doi:10.4319/lo.1994.39.5.1044; Strathmann, R.R., 1967. Estimating the organic carbon content of phytoplankton from cell volume or plasma volume. <i>Limnol. Oceanogr.</i> 12, 411–418. doi:10.4319/lo.1967.12.3.0411; Tomas, C.R., 1997. <i>Identifying Marine Diatoms and Dinoflagellates</i> . New York, Academic Press, 858 pp.

Table 6. Data dictionary: description of the variables (i.e., columns) in Carbon-to-Chl *a* ratio dataset.

Column name	Description	Units	Code explanation	Data format	Missing data code
<i>C:Ch a</i>	<i>It is an in situ derived C:Chl a ratio</i>	<i>mg C mg Chl⁻¹</i>	<i>C = carbon biomass; Chl a = chlorophyll a concentration.</i>		
<i>long</i>	<i>Longitude, E</i>	<i>degrees</i>			
<i>lat</i>	<i>Latitude, N</i>	<i>degrees</i>			
<i>R/V</i>	<i>Research Vessel</i>	<i>voyage number and vessel name</i>	<i>R/V: PV, Professor Vodyanitsky; PK, Professor Kolesnikov.</i>		

Table 7. Data provenance

Dataset title	Dataset DOI or URL	Creator (name & email)	Contact (name & email)
<i>Black Sea Data Base, 2003</i>	<i>Supplied with Ocean Base 3.07 DBMS/NATO SfP-971818 ODBMS Black Sea Project. July 15, 2003.</i>	<i>The database was prepared within the framework of the NATO TU Black Sea Project.</i>	